

MALABANIAS INTEGRATED SCHOOL

Tamarind Street, Clarkview Subdivision, Malabantias, Angeles City

Senior High School Department

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PRACTICAL RESEARCH 1

RESEARCH PAPER

The Impact of Artificial Intelligence Technology on the Learning of Grade 11 Senior High School Students

A Research Paper

Submitted to
Malabantias Integrated School
in partial fulfillment of the requirements for
Practical Research 1

Prepared by:

(Names Withheld for Privacy)

Grade 11 – Aristotle
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ABSTRACT

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This study explores the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI), particularly ChatGPT, on students' learning habits, critical thinking skills, and overall academic performance. As AI tools become more easily available, students tend to use them to handle challenging tasks and accomplish academic work. But this reliance raises concerns about accuracy, independent learning, and cognitive development. Through qualitative thematic analysis of responses from students, the study determines significant themes including AI as a learning tool, its impact on independent thought, and psychological and behavioral effects. Results indicate that although AI supports understanding, excessive dependence decreases critical thinking abilities, lowers motivation levels, and creates problems on academic integrity. Students further expressed alarm over AI-generated inaccuracies, necessitating them to cross-check information from other sources. The study highlights the need for a balanced approach to AI usage in education, ensuring that students develop self-reliance while benefiting from technological advancements.

Key words: *Artificial Intelligence, Student Learning*

CHAPTER 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

In today's modern society, technology, especially Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become an essential part of students' academic lives. Over the past years, Artificial Intelligence has progressed over time which has sparked discussions and debates regarding its role in improving Human Intelligence (HUMINT). While some may argue that it improves on how to think, solve and improve human development, others may claim that it promotes deficiency and reduces the initial role of human Cognitive Abilities (CA).

Previous studies highlight both benefits and drawbacks of AI in education. Dergaa et al. (2024) asserted that overdependence on AI for cognitive tasks can decrease mental stimulation, which can cause reductions in critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity, especially among youth whose cognitive development is still in progress. Similarly, Carr (2020) warns how digital distractions, artificial intelligence, and the rise of multitasking weaken deep thinking, memory retention, and attention span over time.

On the other hand, some researchers suggest that AI can enhance learning when used moderately. Ibanez (2023) said that the use of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) tools can improve students' critical thinking skills, as moderate use helps them analyze, evaluate, and process information more effectively. However, Shanmugasundaram and Tamilarasu (2023) argue that excessive dependence on digital tools such as AI and social media could have a negative impact on attention, memory, and decision-making skills, thus potentially influencing cognitive functions in the long term.

While previous studies have considered the impact of AI on university students and professionals, there is limited study focusing on how AI impacts high school students in a ICT strand a group that is more exposed to AI-powered learning tools, High school students are at a crucial point where critical thinking, problem-solving, and cognitive independence are still developing. This study attempts to cover this gap by examining Grade 11 ICT students' lived experiences and determining whether AI increases or weakens their intellectual capabilities.

The researchers will aim to establish whether AI increases students' intelligence by increasing learning efficiency or whether it contributes to dependency, reducing critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. By analyzing both perspectives, this study will provide insight on the cognitive impact of AI on Grade 11 Senior High School students.

Statement of the Problem

The challenge of understanding how technology particularly Artificial Intelligence (AI) affects human intelligence is the objective of this research. AI plays a significant role in the modern world, but it is unclear how it affects cognitive functions like memory, learning, and problem-solving. Given how AI is widely used in education, understanding its impact is crucial. If not properly examined, it may influence how AI is integrated into daily life and learning as technology advances.

The researchers will seek to answer the following questions:

1. How does artificial intelligence influence the Grade 11 Senior High School students' ability to adapt to new situations?
2. What are the effects of the use of artificial intelligence to students' learning?
3. Based from the results of the study, what output can be crafted?

Theoretical Framework

This study is guided by the Extended Mind Theory (EMT) and Cognitive Offloading Theory (COT). EMT suggests that technology, like AI, computers, and digital tools, acts as an extension of the human mind to assist learners in storing, processing, and retrieving information more effectively. This theory is used in the study as it assesses whether Grade 11 students use AI as an aid to enhance learning and solving problems or whether they become dependent on it and thus minimize independent thinking.

While this, COT describes how people transfer thinking tasks to external tools instead of employing their own mind. This study uses COT to determine if the over-dependence of students on AI and internet sources undermines memory recall, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills.

Finally, Anderson & Krathwohl's Revised Bloom's Taxonomy (2016) classifies cognitive processes into six levels: remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating, and creating. This model provides a structured approach of studying how AI affects students' capacity to participate in higher-order thinking abilities, like problem-solving and critical analysis, which are fundamental for intellectual growth.

By integrating these theories, this study aims to determine whether technology serves as a cognitive enhancer or contributes to a decline in intellectual development among Grade 11 students.

Significance of the Study

This study is an important topic that will benefit the following Individuals:

Students. depend on technology nowadays. As for how it affects them in their daily life, it can help them learn what they are doing and what they are not, learn at their own pace and provides an understanding into how technology can be used in critical thinking, problem solving and most importantly intellectual development.

Educators. are now supported by digital tools and equipment, in this study it shows the various reasons on how technology affects adolescents and impacts their cognitive capabilities. With this information it enables teachers to guide their students through technology, and thus educating them on how it may affect them.

Parents. will be equipped with knowledge on how technology affects their children's intellectual abilities. It also helps them to make important decisions about the extensive use of screen time, digital services, and the use of educational learning applications.

Future Researchers. are to be guided now that technology like AI advances and changes throughout time, it advances its purpose and impact. This research can help future researchers by providing guidance and support when they perform a study that uses this as the basis for comparison of how technology shifts its influence.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The research uses a phenomenological design to explore students' lived experiences with AI in learning. Purposive sampling was used to select 10 ICT students who use AI tools actively. Given that this is qualitative research, we maximized depth over breadth through sampling a small but rich information sample. The sample size was determined based on the principle of data saturation, ensuring that no new insights emerged after multiple interviews.

The study is limited only to Malabanas Integrated School (MIS) and does not cover other schools. The selection of 10 students allows for in-depth qualitative analysis while maintaining flexibility in data collection. This focused approach ensures a detailed understanding of how technology influences intelligence, helping to develop better educational strategies.

Definition of Terms

In this section, the terms are hereby defined, technically and operationally:

Human Intelligence

Technical Definition. Human intelligence is the ability to learn from experience, solve problems, and apply knowledge in various contexts (ScienceDirect, 2024).

Operational Meaning. In this study, human intelligence pertains to the cognitive abilities of Grade 11 students, particularly their critical thinking, adaptability, and problem-solving skills when engaging with AI-based learning tools.

Technology

Technical Definition. Technology is the application of scientific knowledge to create tools, systems, and processes that improve efficiency and problem-solving capabilities (Merriam-Webster, 2025).

Operational Meaning. In this study, technology refers to Artificial Intelligence (AI) and digital learning tools that assist Grade 11 students in accessing, processing, and understanding educational content.

Acronyms

AI: Artificial Intelligence

CA: Cognitive Abilities

DT: Digital Tools

GAI: Generative Artificial Intelligence

HUMINT: Human Intelligence

ICT: Information and Communication Technology

MIS: Malabanas Integrated School

SHS: Senior High School

TVL: Technical Vocational Livelihood

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

Local Related Literature and Studies

In their study, Milloria et al. (2024) examined how AI-integrated teaching affected students' performance in Grade 11 senior high school. They identified that using ChatGPT 3.5 on formative evaluations improved learning, engagement, and knowledge retention by the learners. But raised some concerns about the data privacy, security, and academic integrity of students, they also spoke for ethical regulations in AI-based education. While AI helps learning better, proper regulation and continuous monitoring should be implemented to ensure that it is being used responsibly in schools.

Similarly, the study of Bulawan et al. (2025), which focused on the impact of generative AI on students' engagement in learning, their findings shows that technology such as AI applications enhanced learning and classroom participation. But the research also brings some concerns regarding how students over relied on AI to the point that it leads to laziness and plagiarism. In conclusion, while AI provides big advantages, its ethical and proper application is crucial in ensuring academic integrity and that students develop critical thinking and independent learning skills.

A study examined by Pimentel et al. (2024) shows the advantages of AI chatbots on student engagement. The outcome indicated was that AI chatbots boosted personalized learning and critical thinking but raised issues regarding hands-on learning activities.

Quesada (2017) examined the influence of Information Communication Technology (ICT) on students' cognitive skills, particularly reasoning, decision-making, and problem-solving. Interactive and dynamic digital learning spaces were found to enhance student performance, though other studies report negative effects. Even primarily based on student and teacher feedback, the study revealed ICT's role in enhancing engagement and motivation.

Since then, artificial intelligence has been an advantage to the learning methods of socialization and mental well-being for students. Antipolo et al. (2024) uses the terms technological innovation including digital resources, online education tools, and learning devices such as computers, mobile phones, and the internet. These technologies enhance communication and collaboration among the students but also result in distractions, over-screening, and potential unhealthy effects on the health practices and mindsets of the students. The study points out how the impact of these innovations differs according to the gender of students, study strand, and school type, calling for an orderly integration and proper monitoring.

Foreign Related Literature and Studies

Globally, the rapid development of artificial intelligence has radically influenced human behavior and the intellectual capabilities of students. Vieriu and Petrea (2024) identify in their study that AI supports learning through customization and enhanced academic achievement but also has threats such as over-reliance and diminished critical thinking. It highlights the misuse of AI that can lead to an issue in cognitive ability, thereby affecting learners' ability to think for themselves. The study underscores the need for a better application of AI to prevent academic dishonesty. This indicates the need to achieve a balance between the benefits of AI and its detrimental effect on student intelligence.

Similarly, Zhai et al. (2024) dealt with the impact of AI on students, particularly how they utilize it in their learning environment. It is clear from their study, how overdependence on AI compromises beneficial cognitive skills like the method to think, decide and reason out. The study tells that AI is a powerful tool but implications like misinformation, biased algorithms, and privacy invasion are setting a dangerous path to those who use it. It also focuses on the necessity of solving such issues on acquiring knowledge about reversing cognitive impacts and bringing in a less ethically-questionable AI into education.

Gerlich (2025) explores the influence of AI tools on critical thinking, with cognitive offloading being identified as a determining factor. The results indicate a negative influence of frequent AI usage on critical thinking ability, with users relying more on AI to process information. Younger participants showed a higher tendency to rely on AI tools, which affected their capacity to think critically.

A book by Monteith et al. (2023) explores the risks of AI-generated misinformation, highlighting how generative AI can generate factual errors, fabricated sources, and misleading advice, potentially influencing decision-making. This undermines the bigger concern of AI's reliability, which may also impact students' learning and critical thinking. Addressing AI-powered misinformation is essential in education to ensure students develop a clear perception and avoid overreliance on inaccurate information.

In contrast, Iqbal and Iqbal (2024) explore the influence of AI on the cognitive ability and academic performance of students in terms of learning attitudes and critical thinking. The study shows that AI has a positive effect on learning outcomes if learners are directly involved in critical thinking while using AI tools. Further, the study highlights that the attitude towards learning among students plays a major role in making AI work because those who have a firm will to study benefit more from their studies. The findings indicate that learning outcomes and cognitive skills can be enhanced through AI if used wisely and not passively relied upon.

Kundu and Bej (2025) highlight that while AI enhances student learning, it also poses psychological challenges such as dependency, anxiety, and cognitive overload. Excessive dependence on AI can weaken critical thinking and social flexibility. These effects can be minimized by developing digital literacy and ethical use of AI in ensuring students' psychological health.

CHAPTER 3

METHODS OF STUDY AND SOURCES OF DATA

Research Design

This research study will be using Phenomenological research design, which focuses on understanding human experiences related to the impact of AI on human intelligence. Phenomenology is a qualitative research approach that aims to explore and describe individuals' lived experiences with a particular phenomenon to understand its meaning from their perspectives (Creswell & Poth, 2018). By using a phenomenological approach, the researchers can gather data or insights from Grade 11, senior high school students aged 16-17, about how they used or how they were influenced by AI daily and their academic lives. This design is related, as the opinions of the students are related to their experiences and the interaction, they made with how they use and respond to AI. This will give the researcher the opportunity to gather important qualitative data that will give the future readers of this study on how it would improve the thinking development in adolescents.

Participants of the Study

This study will cover Grade 11, Senior High School (SHS) students aged 16-17 from the strand of Technical-Vocational Livelihood, Information and Communication Technology (TVL-ICT) with 10 participants selected using purposive sampling, ensuring that they have relevant experiences with technology use in learning.

To minimize bias, participants were selected from two different sections (Aristotle & Aquinas) to provide a diverse range of experiences. Also, we looked at both positive and negative experiences with AI to ensure that the study provides a balanced view and not a particular one.

The research focused on ICT students because these are individuals that are exposed mostly to technology such as AI tools and digital learning materials in their studies. Quesada (2017) examined the effect of ICT on students' cognitive abilities, underlining its role in reasoning, decision-making, and problem-solving. Although the study does not directly say ICT students are most exposed, it suggests that students who take part in ICT-related strands acquire these skills through the use of technology.

Teenagers in this age group are among the most active users of AI for schoolwork. Pew Research Center (2025) discovered that roughly a quarter of American teens 13-17 years old have used ChatGPT for schoolwork, which doubled compared to last year. While this study is based in the U.S., it reflects a growing trend that may also apply to Filipino students, especially as AI becomes more common in education.

Their experiences provide valuable insights into whether technology enhances intelligence or encourages dependency, making them an ideal group for this research.

Instrument

This study will use a researcher-made questionnaire as the primary data-gathering instrument. Researcher-made questionnaire refers to the instrument to be used in research prepared or crafted by the researcher himself or herself. Canonizado (2024) defines a researcher-made questionnaire as an instrument crafted by the researcher, incorporating expert feedback to align with study objectives.

The questionnaire will explore how AI influences students' study habits, learning methods, and academic performance, the challenges they encounter in using AI for learning, its impact on cognitive abilities such as problem-solving, critical thinking, and memory retention, and how it affects efficiency and focus in their studies.

By using a researcher-made questionnaire, this research ensures that data will be directly proportional to the objectives of the study. Through this method, it gives a better understanding of whether AI are tools for enhancing cognitive abilities or make students dependent on them.

Data Collection

Data collection for the study titled “The Impact of Artificial Intelligence Technology on the Learning of Grade 11 Senior High School Students” will primarily focus on in-depth interviews. This method was chosen to provide a deeper understanding of individuals' experiences, particularly Grade 11 students aged 16-17 years old, their perspectives, and their understanding of the complex role between AI and human intelligence.

Structured interviews will be used in this study, allowing participants to better express their experiences on whether AI impacts their intellectual capabilities or not. To ensure ethical research practices, informed consent will be taken from all the participants prior to the initiation of the interview process. The consent will be accompanied by a proper explanation of the purpose of the study, voluntary participation, the right to withdraw at any point in time, and confidentiality of their answers.

Ethical Consideration

The study titled "The Impact of Artificial Intelligence Technology on the Learning of Grade 11 Senior High School Students" emphasizes the importance of safeguarding participants' rights, confidentiality, and research integrity.

The researchers will make sure that all participants participate in the study voluntarily by seeking informed consent prior to conducting interviews. They will be informed in detail about the purpose of the study, their role, and their right to withdraw at any time without any repercussions. For privacy and confidentiality purposes, personal details will be anonymized and used for academic purposes only.

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Moreover, participants will answer questions without external pressure, and their answers will not be affected by third parties. Institutional policies of the Department of Education (DepEd) and ethical standards will be strictly adhered to in order to maintain fairness, respect, and safety during the research process.

Through these ethical practices, the researchers hope to provide a safe environment where students can openly share their experiences about AI's effect on their intelligence.

Data Analysis

The researchers will use Thematic analysis as the basis for the data analysis, in the study titled "The Impact of Artificial Intelligence Technology on the Learning of Grade 11 Senior High School Students". McLeod (2024) defines thematic analysis as a method used to identify, analyze, and interpret patterns of shared meaning (themes) within qualitative data, such as interviews, focus group discussions, surveys, or other textual sources. The researchers will uncover how AI impacts human intelligence. Thematic analysis can be used to determine how individuals aged 16-17 years old affect their cognitive and intellectual capabilities and how their actions are influenced after using AI. In conclusion, Thematic analysis is the method that can be used to explain the positive and negative impact of AI on human intelligence.

CHAPTER 4

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of the data that was gathered. Using thematic analysis, responses from Grade 11 ICT Senior High School students were organized into key themes. These themes show the experiences of students' regarding the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on their cognitive abilities, intellectual development and its role in academic habits.

Theme 1: AI as a Learning Tool and Its Impact on Understanding

Among the main themes that was identified in the responses is the role of AI as a learning aid. Many students admit that AI tools like ChatGPT help them in understanding hard tasks. But others reported that AI provides incorrect or irrelevant answers, requiring them to seek additional sources of information.

Supporting Responses:

"Sometimes ChatGPT does not provide the exact answer. So I just copy my classmates' answers." (Participant 1)

"It affects me in a way that I turn into a very lazy person in that I cannot learn any other methods that I could come up with because I know that I have AI on my side and I'm very dependent on it." (Participant 3)

"Oo, pag nag serearch ako tapos diko maintindihan yung sa AI, na resolve ko siya kung san nag search pako sa iba like sa Google, para mas maintindihan ko yung sinabi ni ChatGPT, kasi mali minsan." (Participant 8)

The findings show that while AI serves as an accessible and helpful learning tool, especially for students, it can also lead to dependency and laziness. Some students rely heavily on AI, which affects their ability to think critically and seek alternative learning methods.

These results align with Milloria et al. (2024), whose study revealed that AI such as ChatGPT enhanced student engagement and retention of knowledge. Yet their study also identified issues related to data accuracy and academic integrity. Similarly, Vieriu and Petrea (2025) noted that though AI enhances learning, it promotes risk like excessive dependence and weakens critical thinking.

Theme 2: Balancing AI Use and Independent Learning

This theme explores students' overdependence on AI and its impact on their capacity for independent learning. Although AI enables students to access information quickly, there were some participants who confessed they over-relied on it, which impacted their motivation to think critically.

Supporting Responses:

"AI affects my studies in a way that I depend more on AI." (Participant 5)

"Yes, I encounter challenges by using artificial intelligence because artificial intelligence or AI is not accurate sometimes. If you do not guide him, he will not answer. It's not appropriate." (Participant 6)

"It makes it easy for me to study my lesson, because ChatGPT is here to guide me and help me to understand it." (Participant 9)

The researchers found that over-reliance on AI puts students in a lack of critical thinking and learning independently, by using AI students' ability to think critically affects their motivation and their whole study habits.

These results are supported by studies conducted by Bulawan et al. (2025), indicating that AI tools enhance student participation, but causes academic laziness and plagiarism. Likewise, Iqbal and Iqbal (2024) argued that AI contributes positively to learning outcomes if learners are engaged actively in critical thinking when utilizing AI tools instead of merely depending on answers.

Theme 3: Emotional, Behavioral, and Psychological Effects of AI Use

The themes explored reveal the impact of AI on students' psychological health in terms of study habits and load on their mind. Some students reported feelings of self-doubt and stress when comparing their work to AI-generated responses, indicating potential anxiety for certain individuals.

Supporting Responses:

"It makes my brain dumb, and I rely too much to the point that I need AI in the implied questions." (Participant 2)

"It negatively affects my studies in a way that I cannot sleep earlier than I used to and that I woke up earlier again so that I could use AI again after I answered all the activities that I needed to complete or accomplish. And then I sleep, and then I wake up. That's just it." (Participant 3)

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"Nababawasan niya yung confidence ko kapag nag sasagot ako, nag ooverthink ako kung tama ba talaga yung sinagot ko dahil pag nag-AI ako is accurate naman yung ibang sagot." (Participant 10)

The findings reveal that while AI helps in learning, it also has an impact on students' most important aspect of life, which is their mental health. Students' emotional, behavioral, and psychological well being were affected due to AI. It was discovered that some students overthink and experience lack of sleep, while others believed that AI made their brains dumb.

These align with Antipolo et al. (2024), which highlight that AI tools improve collaboration but at the same time also lead to distraction and unhealthy learning behavior. Kundu and Bej (2025) also said the same, explaining more that over-usage AI leads to dependency, anxiety and cognitive overload in a psychological overview.

Theme 4: AI Dependency and Its Consequences

This theme focuses on how AI dependency affects students' ability to function independently and naturally in academic settings. Several participants acknowledged that AI had made them less inclined to engage in manual problem-solving.

Supporting Responses:

"AI negatively affects me by making me more lazy and needy as well as being dependent on AI for particular tasks." (Participant 2)

"It doesn't lower my IQ, but it reduces my skills, I'd say, and I do lack the ability to manage myself because, like I said, I'm being dependent on it too much. I'm being too left out in any of the subjects that I need to learn or the lessons that I need to cut out." (Participant 3)

"Siguro it affects my efficiency in my studies and I am being lazy to even answer my assignments because in one click AI will respond to you." (Participant 6)

The researchers found that students' dependency on AI reduced their skills and efficiency in their studies. This indicates that excessive use of AI diminishes their ability to think independently, ultimately affecting their study habits and learning methods.

These results correspond with the study of Bulawan et al. (2025), who found that being dependent on AI leads to academic laziness and reduces intellectual effort. Same with Zhai et al. (2024) who emphasized that AI overuse weakens students' reasoning and decision-making skills.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

This study examines the experiences of Grade 11 ICT Senior High School students regarding the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on their intelligence, cognitive abilities along with academic habits and development. Through thematic analysis, four major themes emerged:

AI as a Learning Tool, Its Impact on Understanding, and Independent Learning

Students agreed that ChatGPT and other AI tools help them understand difficult tasks. But they also said that AI responses were inaccurate and needed to be confirmed by other sources such as Google. Some students admitted that AI made studying easier, but others recognized that excessive reliance on AI affected their critical thinking skills.

Emotional, Behavioral, and Psychological Effects of AI Use and Its Consequences

Students' confidence, focus, and tendency to delay tasks were impacted by using AI. Some students may have experienced anxiety due to comparing their work with AI-generated responses. While AI-assisted learning helped students understand new ideas, excessive dependence on it resulted in a decrease in their ability to solve problems and think critically.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The study found that ChatGPT and other AI tools help students in comprehending difficult tasks. Students also pointed out that AI answers were sometimes incorrect and needed proof from additional sources, like Google. Some students said that using AI too much had a negative impact on their ability to think critically, while others thought it was helpful for studying.
2. Additionally, AI use had emotional, behavioral, and psychological effects on students. Their confidence, focus, and tendency to delay tasks were impacted, with some experiencing anxiety when comparing their work to AI-generated responses. Although AI-assisted learning helped students grasp new ideas, excessive dependence on it led to a decline in their problem-solving abilities and independent thinking.

Recommendations

From the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. For Educators – Schools need to incorporate AI literacy courses into the curriculum, instructing students in how to critically analyze AI-generated information and balanced AI assistance against independent problem-solving. Educators should design assignments that require students to verify AI-generated content and provide their own analysis to strengthen critical thinking skills.
2. For Students – Students must and should develop cross-referencing skills, verifying AI-generated information with credible academic sources. Rather than replicating AI answers, they should learn to summarize and critically analyze AI outputs to improve independent thinking and analytical abilities.
3. For Parents – Parents should monitor their children’s AI usage and guide them in responsible technology use and encourage discussions about the advantages and limitations of AI to promote awareness and balance.
4. For Future Researchers – Future studies should examine the impact of various AI literacy approaches on student learning outcomes in the long term. Longitudinal research could measure whether AI introduction at an early age impacts long-term cognitive skills and problem-solving skills.

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Appendix A Permission Letter

March 10, 2025

Sir,

We, the undersigned Grade 11 students of Malabantias Integrated School, are currently conducting a research study as part of our Practical Research 1 subject. Our study, titled “*The Impact of Artificial Intelligence Technology on the Learning of Grade 11 Senior High School Students,*” aims to understand modern technology, especially Artificial Intelligence, how it affects the cognitive abilities of students' study habits particularly in their way of solving, memorizing and thinking.

In line with this, we respectfully request your permission to conduct face-to-face interviews within the school perimeter. Specifically, we intend to use semi-structured interviews, involving Grade 11 Senior High School students aged 16-17 years old from the strand of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) among sections Aristotle and Aquinas.

This study will be conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines set by the Department of Education including the right of informed consent, voluntary participation, confidentiality, and data privacy. Participants will be fully informed about the study's purpose, and their participation will be entirely voluntary, with the right to withdraw at any time. The collected data will remain confidential and used solely for academic purposes.

We would greatly appreciate your approval of our request. Should you require further details, we are more than willing to provide additional information. Thank you very much for your time and consideration.

Sincerely,

The Researchers
Malabantias Integrated School

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Appendix B Instrument/Tool

Dear Participant/s,

The researchers are currently conducting a study titled “The Impact of Artificial Intelligence Technology on the Learning of Grade 11 Senior High School Students”. This research aims to understand how technology, particularly Artificial Intelligence (AI), influences students' learning, problem-solving, and critical thinking abilities.

The collected information will come from 10 participants among Grade 11, Technical Vocational Livelihood, Information and Communication Technology (TVL-ICT) students aged 16-17 years old.

We assure you that we will treat your responses and identity with confidentiality, using them solely for research purposes.

PART I: Demographic Profile

Name: (optional) _____ Section: _____
Age: _____ Sex: Male Female Strand: _____

Primary device used for studying:

- Smartphone
- Computer/Laptop
- Tablet
- Others (Please specify): _____

Do you use AI-powered tools like ChatGPT, Cici, Gemini, or other smart study apps to help with your studies?

- Yes No

Instructions: Please answer all questions honestly based on your personal experience with technology, particularly Artificial Intelligence, as a student. There are no right or wrong answers. Keep your responses clear and concise. Your answers will remain confidential and used solely for research purposes. Thank you for your participation.

PART II: Influence of Technology

1. Have you encountered any challenges posed by artificial intelligence in your academic journey? If yes, how did you resolve it?
2. How does artificial intelligence affect your study habits, learning methods and academic performance?

PART III: Effects of Technology

3. What is the impact of artificial intelligence in your intellectual capabilities such as problem-solving, critical thinking and memory retention?
4. How does using artificial intelligence negatively affect your efficiency in your studies?

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Appendix C Consent Letter

Title of the Study: The Impact of Artificial Intelligence Technology on the Learning of Grade 11 Senior High School Students

Dear Participant,

We, the researchers, are currently conducting a research study to explore the impact of technology, particularly Artificial Intelligence (AI) on human cognitive intelligence. The researchers seek to identify both of its positive and negative effects on human intelligence and will analyze its contribution to education and cognitive skill development.

Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary. If you choose to participate, you will be asked to complete a questionnaire that will take approximately 10-15 minutes. You may skip any question you are not comfortable answering and may withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences.

Confidentiality:

All responses will be kept strictly confidential and used solely for research purposes. No personally identifiable information will be shared.

Potential Benefits and Risks:

While there are no direct risks associated with participation, the study will contribute to enhancing the ways to improve the usage of technology, promoting awareness, and potentially developing policies that facilitate effective technological interactions in the field of education and development.

Contact Information:

If you have any questions or concerns about this study, you may contact:

By signing below, you acknowledge that:

- ✓ You have read and understood the purpose of the study.
- ✓ You voluntarily agree to participate.
- ✓ You understand that you may withdraw at any time without any penalty.

Participant's Name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

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Appendix D Validation Letter and Form

February 27, 2025

Subject: Request for Validation of Interview Questionnaire

Sir,

I hope this letter finds you well. We, the researchers, are formally requesting your expertise in validating an interview questionnaire that will be used in our research titled “*The Impact of Artificial Intelligence Technology on the Learning of Grade 11 Senior High School Students.*” Our goal is to determine whether technology improves human intelligence or reduces cognitive functions such as memory, learning, and problem-solving.

The interview questionnaire has been designed to gather valuable insights from *Grade 11-Technical-Vocational-Livelihood, Information and Communications Technology (TVL-ICT) students aged 16-17 years old.* Its validity is crucial in ensuring the reliability and credibility of the study. Given your extensive knowledge and experience in mathematics, statistical analysis, and engineering problem-solving, your feedback on the clarity, relevance, and appropriateness of the questions would be highly beneficial.

Enclosed with this letter is a copy of the questionnaire along with a validation form. We would greatly appreciate it if you could review the instrument and provide your evaluation and suggestions for improvement. Should you require any additional information or modifications, please do not hesitate to reach out.

Your assistance in this endeavor will significantly contribute to the study’s success. We sincerely appreciate your time and expertise, and we look forward to your positive response.

Thank you very much.

Warm regards,

*The Researchers
Malabanas Integrated School*

The Impact of AI Technology on the Learning of Grade 11 Senior High School Students

Title of the Research: The Impact of Artificial Intelligence Technology on the Learning of Grade 11 Senior High School Students

Researcher's Name: [REDACTED]

Institution: Malabaniyas Integrated School

Date: February 27, 2025

Dear Validator,

Thank you for taking the time to review and validate this interview questionnaire. Your expertise and feedback are essential in ensuring that the questions are clear, relevant, and appropriate for the study. Kindly evaluate each item based on the criteria below and provide comments or suggestions where necessary.

PART I: Validator's Information

Name: _____

Position/Designation: _____

Field of Expertise: _____

Institution/Organization: _____

Email: _____

Contact Number: _____

PART II: Validation Criteria

Please rate each question based on the following criteria using the scale below:

Scale Description

- 4 Highly Acceptable (No revision needed)
- 3 Acceptable (Minor revisions needed)
- 2 Needs Improvement (Major revisions needed)
- 1 Not Acceptable (Must be revised or removed)

PART III: Questionnaire Evaluation

Question Number	Clarity (1-4)	Relevance (1-4)	Appropriateness (1-4)	Comments/Suggestions
1				
2				
3				
4				

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PART IV: General Comments and Recommendations

1. Are there any questions that need to be revised or clarified? If yes, please specify:

2. Are there any additional questions you would suggest including?

3. Do you have any other recommendations to improve the questionnaire?

PART V: Validator's Certification

I certify that I have reviewed the interview questionnaire and provided my evaluation based on my expertise and knowledge.

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Appendix E
Documentation

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